

EFFECT OF MOISTURE CONTENT ON MAIZE SHELLING SPEED USING A MANUALLY OPERATED
HAND SHELLE IN MUBI, ADAMAWA STATE.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of moisture content on maize shelling speed using a manually operated hand Sheller (cone type). Twenty (20) unthreshed maize cob samples (A-J) were used for the study. The samples were analysed in the laboratory for parameters such as weight of samples before and after drying, moisture content and shelling speed. The result indicated that sample J, after sixty nine hours (69th) oven drying recorded the lowest moisture content(15.10% wb) and the fastest shelling speed (0.75 rev. per. Sec) compared to sample A (24 h drying time) which had the highest moisture content (28.99%wb) and lowest shelling speed(0.96 rev. per. sec). It was observed that sample J with the shortest shelling duration had the smallest grain weight (84.2g), while sample 'A' recorded larger grain weight (162.9g) due to differing moisture content of the maize grains. The data generated was analysed and compared using statistical means, percentages and figures for pictorial presentation. The pearson correlation between shelling speed and moisture content correlated weakly (r=0.4). Generally the result revealed that the longer the drying period the more moisture were extracted from the samples. Hence the lower the moisture content then the faster the shelling speed. It is recommended that maize cobs be dried properly to enable easier and faster shelling operation with less fatigue and minimum grain damage.

KEYWORDS: Shelling time, moisture content, drying time, shelling speed, maize grain and grain weight.

INTRODUCTION.

Maize undergoes many post harvest operations before consumption, of which shelling is of great importance. Shelling is the removal or separation of the natural casing or husk, and is performed prior to storage or processing operations. Shelling is mostly carried out by women, and is very labour intensive and time consuming (Fandohan 2004). According to Makanjuola (1978), the average human power needed for shelling exercise is 0.1 kilowatt. Some harvested grain crops are tied in bags and tractor passes made over them. The weight of the tractor on the cobs separates the grain from the cobs. The mixture of grains and chaff are winnowed to obtain clean grains. There are two classes of shelling machines, hand- and power operated shellers. Different types and sizes of manually operated maize shelling machines have been constructed, such as cone, crocodile and atlas shaped types. The cone type operation requires single cob to be fed at a time, the machine consists of welded three or four lines of teeth inside a cylindrically shaped metal sheet. The moisture content of the maize grain greatly influences the speed of shelling. Moisture content is a term used to describe the amount of water present in a farm product. This study therefore intends to investigate the effect of moisture content on maize shelling speed using a manually operated hand shelling device (cone type) in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in the period when maize was harvested at Mubi, Adamawa state. This is a period that lies between the beginning of October to November ending.

Mubi is located in the northern part of Adamawa State, Nigeria. It lies between latitude 9^o 26¹ and 10^o10¹ N, and between longitudes 13^o 1¹ and 13^o 44¹ E. It borders Borno state to the west, Maiha and Hong L.G.A. to the south and Michika L.G..A. to the north, while, its eastern boundary belts the Nigeria-Cameroon borders. The area has a landmass of 506.4 square kilometres (km) with a population of 759,045 at a density of 160.5 person per square kilometre(Nwagboso and Uyanga 1999). The area has a wet and dry climates. Dry season lasts for a minimum of

five months (November to March), while the wet season spans between April and October. Mean annual rainfall usually ranges between 700mm to 1.050mm (Adebayo 2004).

The shelling device.

The device used for the research is a manually cone shape maize shelling type (plate 1). It is a cone shape metal with four (4) lines of teeth arranged in a cylindrically cone shaped metal, running from end to end.

Laboratory Study

Maize cobs were obtained from the Federal polytechnic Mubi school of Agriculture demonstration farm. Twenty (20) unthreshed maize cobs were randomly selected. The weight of ten (10) cobs were determined using a sensitive digital balance (metler balance 2000). The samples were oven dried in the laboratory. The samples were oven dried at 60°C for period of 24 to 69 h, and there weight determined after drying.

The samples were brought out consecutively at an interval of five h, and then reweighed. Each sample was then introduced into the hand Sheller (cone type) plate 1, where the maize cob was rotated inside the cone by one hand with an average power of 0.1kw (Makanjuola 1978) while the Sheller was held in the other hand. The rotation of the cob against the teeth removes the grains from the maize cob. A stop watch was used to record the shelling time of each operation. The output of every operation was also weighed and recorded. The moisture content of the samples (A-J), were computed from the result using a formula given as (A.O.A.C., 2000):

$$\frac{M_0 - M_1}{M_0} \times 100\% \text{ (wb)} \quad (1)$$

Where M_0 = Weight before drying.

M_1 = Weight after drying.

Data Analysis

1. The data generated was analysed and compared using statistical means, percentages and figures for pictorial presentation. The pearson correlation coefficient was also used to compare the shelling speed and moisture content given as (Suleiman, 1997):

$$r = \frac{XY}{\sqrt{(X^2)(Y^2)}} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1 Moisture content vs drying time

Fig. 2 Shelling speed vs moisture content.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result on moisture content, drying time, shelling speed, weight of samples before and after drying and the weight of the threshed grains are presented in table 1. The drying time (h) of the samples (A-J) shows that the drying time (at 5 h interval) was inversely proportional to the moisture content. At each drying phase the longer the drying period, then the less the moisture content and weight of the threshed grains. Sample A with the shortest drying time (24 h) recorded the highest (28.99%) moisture content at longest shelling speed (0.96 rev. per. sec.). A reverse situation was noticed with sample J which had the longest drying time (69 h) to yield the least moisture content (15.10%) and fastest shelling speed (0.75 rev. per. sec.). It was observed that sample J with the lowest moisture content had the smallest grain weight (84.2g), while sample A recorded larger grain weight value (162.9g) due to differing moisture content of the maize grain. It was also observed that there was a difference in weight of samples before and after drying at each drying phase Sample C recorded a weight of 139.3g before drying and 102.4g after drying.

Table 1; Threshing and moisture parameters of the maize samples

Maize samples	Weight of sample before drying(g)	Drying time (hr)	Weight of sample after drying(g)	Moisture content (%)	Shelling speed (r.p.s)	Weight of threshed grains (g)
A	311.2	24	221.3	28.99	0.96	162.9
B	324.4	29	234.9	27.69	0.95	153.4
C	139.3	34	102.4	26.59	0.65	121.42
D	146.3	39	108.7	25.70	0.94	130.33
E	198.2	44	153.4	22.60	0.94	129.2
F	243.0	49	192.0	21.09	0.93	104.2
G	240.9	54	195.8	18.72	0.83	104.2
H	201.1	59	165.1	17.90	0.82	92.3
I	211.7	64	175.1	17.39	0.80	98.4
J	297.4	69	252.5	15.10	0.75	84.2

Key: A-J. Maize samples

Fig.1 indicated the relationship between shelling speed and moisture content as directly proportional, while Fig2 presented the maize grain moisture content and drying time, there relationship implied that the drying time was inversely proportional to the moisture content. Hence, the shelling speed and moisture content correlated positively at $r = 0.4$.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The degree of dryness of unthreshed maize has to be considered before subjecting it to any shelling device. It suffices to conclude that maize shelling efficiency is a function of its moisture content. Implying that increase in one translate into the decrease of the other, and vice versa. It is recommended that maize cobs be dried properly to enable easier and faster shelling operation with less fatigue and minimum grain damage.

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Plate 1: Manually operated maize shelling device (cone type) (aerial view)

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